

Polarographic Study of Mixed Ligand (Thioglycolate-Glutamate) Complexes of Cd^{2+} , Pb^{2+} and Tl^+

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The precise nature of complexation of cadmium, lead and thallium with mixed ligand system viz., thioglycolic acid+glutamic acid has been investigated by polarographic technique. It is observed that only a single mixed ligand entity MA_1X_1 is formed. The stability constants have been evaluated.

LITERATURE reveals that mercapto acids and other sulphur containing compounds with active -SH group have gained importance in pharmaceutical, biological and analytical chemistry¹⁻⁴. These ligands have also figured prominently in the sphere of coordination chemistry⁵⁻⁷. As a part of our investigations of the series of the mixed ligand complexes of mercaptans and carboxylic ligands^{8,9} with various metal ions, the present mixed ligand systems with Cd^{2+} , Pb^{2+} and Tl^+ have been studied polarographically using thioglycolate and glutamate as mixed ligands. No report is available in literature on the study of this system and hence the present study was undertaken.

Experimental

Sodium thioglycolate (Evan's Chemetics, Inc., N.Y.) and glutamic acid as potassium salt, were used as the complexing agents. All other reagents used were of B.D.H., AnalaR grade. Stock solutions were prepared in double distilled air free conductivity water. Gelatin (0.01%) was used as maximum suppressor and NH_4NO_3 ($\mu=1.0 M$) as supporting electrolyte. A 'Southern manual polarograph' (Surrey, England) with scalamp galvanometer was used for recording current voltage curves. The capillary characteristics in NH_4NO_3 ($\mu=1.0 M$) at $E_{d.e.} = -0.60$ volt in conjunction with SCE were $m^{2/3}t^{1/6} = 2.3697 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ sec}^{-1/2}$ ($h=65 \text{ cm}$) at 30° . All measurements were done with the cell immersed in a thermostatic bath, controlled at the desired temperatures. Dissolved air was removed by bubbling nitrogen through the cell and necessary correction for the iR drop and residual current were made as usual.

Formation of mixed ligand complexes were studied by recording polarograms of two different sets as described below.

1st set :

1.0 mM Cd^{2+} or Pb^{2+} or Tl^+ , 0.01% gelatin and NH_4NO_3 ($\mu=1.0 M$) with constant glutamate con-

centration ($C_X=20.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) and varying concentration of thioglycolate ($C_A=5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ to $60.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ in case of Cd^{2+} and Pb^{2+} and $10.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ to $80.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ in case of Tl^+).

2nd set :

1.0 mM Cd^{2+} or Pb^{2+} or Tl^+ , 0.01% gelatin and NH_4NO_3 ($\mu=1.0 M$) with constant thioglycolate concentration ($C_A=20.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) and varying concentration of glutamate ($C_X=5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ to $60.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ in case of Cd^{2+} and Pb^{2+} and $10.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ to $80.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ in case of Tl^+).

All the plots of $\log i/i_d - i$ vs $-E_{d.e.}$ yielded straight lines with slopes which agreed with the theoretical value corresponding to $n=2$ for Cd^{2+} and Pb^{2+} system and $n=1$ for Tl^+ system. The mean values of the slope were 0.030 for Cd^{2+} , 0.030 for Pb^{2+} and 0.061 for Tl^+ system showing the reversibility of the reduction. Linear plots of i_d vs $\sqrt{h_{eff}}$ passing through the origin, establish the diffusion controlled nature in each case. The $E_{1/2}$ values were found to shift towards more negative values with increasing concentration of mixed ligands, showing complex formation. The $E_{1/2}$ evaluated from the log plots of various above mentioned C-V curves and corresponding diffusion current values have been recorded (Table 1).

Souchey and Faucherre¹⁰ derived an equation where metal ion forms complex with two ligand species simultaneously in solution. If the complexing reaction of the following type is considered

with the restriction that a single mixed ligand entity MA_iX_j is formed, then the shift in the $E_{1/2}$ of the polarographic wave of the metal ion as a function of concentration of added reagents A and X is given by

$$\Delta E_{1/2} = \frac{2.303 RT}{nF} \log \left[\frac{D \text{ free}}{D \text{ comp.}} \right]^{1/2} - \frac{2.303 RT}{nF} \log K_{MA_iX_j} - i \frac{2.303 RT}{nF} \log C_A - j \frac{2.303 RT}{nF} \log C_X \quad \dots (2)$$

TABLE 1—THIOGLYCOLATE-GLUTAMATE SYSTEM

Sl. No.	Conc. (M)		Cd ²⁺ system		Pb ²⁺ system		Tl ⁺ system	
	C _A	C _X	i _d (μA)	-ΔE _{1/2} (Volt)	i _d (μA)	-ΔE _{1/2} (Volt)	i _d (μA)	-ΔE _{1/2} (Volt)
1.	0.00	0.00	5.66	0.000	7.25	0.000	6.70	0.000
2.	0.005	0.02	5.28	0.186	6.22	0.180	—	—
3.	0.01	0.02	5.00	0.203	5.94	0.198	4.48	0.021
4.	0.02	0.02	4.90	0.221	5.75	0.217	4.38	0.037
5.	0.04	0.02	4.72	0.239	5.56	0.235	4.29	0.054
6.	0.06	0.02	4.53	0.249	5.47	0.246	4.24	0.062
7.	0.01	0.02	—	—	—	—	4.15	0.070
8.	0.02	0.005	5.00	0.202	6.18	0.202	—	—
9.	0.02	0.01	4.81	0.212	5.85	0.208	4.57	0.021
10.	0.02	0.04	4.43	0.230	5.66	0.225	4.52	0.058
11.	0.02	0.06	4.24	0.236	5.56	0.230	4.43	0.063
12.	0.02	0.08	—	—	—	—	4.05	0.069

The ratio D free/D comp. were obtained from the values of limiting current. From plots of ΔE_{1/2} vs -log C_A with C_X kept constant and ΔE_{1/2} vs -log C_X with C_A kept constant, value for 'i' and 'j' can be obtained by intersect method because of differentiation

$$\left[\frac{\partial(\Delta E_{1/2})}{\partial(\log C_A)} \right]_{C_X} = -i \frac{2.303 RT}{nF} \quad (3)$$

$$\left[\frac{\partial(\Delta E_{1/2})}{\partial(\log C_X)} \right]_{C_A} = -j \frac{2.303 RT}{nF} \quad (4)$$

Plot of ΔE_{1/2} vs -log C_A (C_X kept constant), plot (i), and ΔE_{1/2} vs -log C_X (C_A kept constant), plot (ii), yielded straight lines (Fig. 1, curves 1-6) and thus establish the formation of a single mixed ligand

Fig. 1. Curves 1, 3 and 5 : C_X constants, C_A varied, curves 2, 4 and 6 : C_A constant, C_X varied.

entity MA_iX_j. The coordination number 'i' and 'j' of the ligands A and X determined from the plots (i) and (ii) and are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Sl No	Metal ion	'i'	'j'	log K _{MA_iX_j}
1	Cd ²⁺	1.97	1.04	12.45
2	Pb ²⁺	2.05	0.95	12.31
3	Tl ⁺	0.92	0.89	3.99

After obtaining the 'i' and 'j' values, the stability constant, log K_{MA_iX_j}, of the mixed ligand complex is determined using equation (2) and are given in Table 2.

The present investigation clearly reveals the formation of only single mixed ligand species (CdA₂X)⁶⁻ of Cd²⁺, (PbA₂X)⁶⁻ of Pb²⁺ and (TlAX)⁵⁻ of Tl⁺ with mixed ligand thioglycolate-glutamate system.

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